

The verse.

This is how the major set and minor sets of the verse functions, and it goes as followed:

1. Absolute final perpetual seeing something seen, the absolute final perpetual something seen 0.
2. Absolute final perpetual seeing nothing hidden, the absolute final perpetual nothing hidden 0.
3. Finally seeing nothing seen winner, the finally seen 0.
4. Seeing nothing seen winner, the perpetually seen 0.
5. Seeing something hidden winner, paired final 0, extra final 0, which make the outcome of another final 0.
6. 1st seen winner, 1 paired 1, extra 1, which makes the outcome of another 1.
7. 2nd hidden winner, 2 paired 2, extra 2, which makes the outcome of another 2.
8. 3rd seen winner, 3 paired 3, extra 3, which makes the outcome of another 3.
9. Inner hidden inner 1, 4 paired 4, extra 4, which makes the outcome of another 4.
10. Inner hidden inner 2, 5 paired 5, extra 5, which makes the outcome of another 5.
11. Inner hidden inner 3, 6 paired 6, extra 6, which makes the outcome of another 6.
12. Inner hidden inner 4, 7 paired 7, extra 7, which makes the outcome of another 7.
13. Inner hidden inner 5, 8 paired 8, extra 8, which makes the outcome of another 8.
14. Inner hidden inner 6, 9 paired 9, extra 9, which makes the outcome of another 9.
15. Inner hidden inner 7, 10 paired 10, extra 10, which makes the outcome of another 10.
16. Inner hidden inner 8, 11 paired 11, extra 11, which makes the outcome of another 11.
17. Inner hidden inner 9, 12 paired 12, extra 12, which makes the outcome of another 12.
18. Inner hidden inner 10, 13 paired 13, extra 13, which makes the outcome of another 13.
19. Inner hidden inner 11, 14 paired 14, extra 14, which makes the outcome of another 14.
20. Inner hidden inner 12, 15 paired 15, extra 15, which makes the outcome of another 15.
21. Inner hidden inner 13, 16 paired 16, extra 16, which makes the outcome of another 16.
22. Inner hidden inner 14, 17 paired 17, extra 17, which makes the outcome of another 17.
23. Inner hidden inner 15, 18 paired 18, extra 18, which makes the outcome of another 18.
24. Inner hidden inner 16, 19 paired 19, extra 19, which makes the outcome of another 19.

25. Inner hidden inner 17, 20 paired 20, extra 20, which makes the outcome of another 20.
26. Inner hidden inner 18, 21 paired 21, extra 21, which makes the outcome of another 21.
27. Inner hidden inner 19, 22 paired 22, extra 22, which makes the outcome of another 22.
28. Inner hidden inner 20, 23 paired 23, extra 23, which makes the outcome of another 23.
29. Inner hidden inner 21, 24 paired 24, extra 24, which makes the outcome of another 24.
30. Inner hidden inner 22, 25 paired 25, extra 25, which makes the outcome of another 25.
31. Inner hidden inner 23, 26 paired 26, extra 26, which makes the outcome of another 26.
32. Inner hidden inner 24, 27 paired 27, extra 27, which makes the outcome of another 27.
33. Inner hidden inner 25, 28 paired 28, extra 28, which makes the outcome of another 28.
34. Inner hidden inner 26, 29 paired 29, extra 29, which makes the outcome of another 29.
35. Inner hidden inner 27, 30 paired 30, extra 30, which makes the outcome of another 30.
36. Inner hidden inner 28, 31 paired 31, extra 31, which makes the outcome of another 31.
37. Inner hidden inner 29, 32 paired 32, extra 32, which makes the outcome of another 32.
38. Inner hidden inner 30, 33 paired 33, extra 33, which makes the outcome of another 33.
39. Inner hidden inner 31, 34 paired 34, extra 34, which makes the outcome of another 34.
40. Inner hidden inner 32, 35 paired 35, extra 35, which makes the outcome of another 35.
41. Inner hidden inner 33, 36 paired 36, extra 36, which makes the outcome of another 36.
42. Inner hidden inner 34, 37 paired 37, extra 37, which makes the outcome of another 37.
43. Inner hidden inner 35, 38 paired 38, extra 38, which makes the outcome of another 38.
44. Inner hidden inner 36, 39 paired 39, extra 39, which makes the outcome of another 39.

45. Inner hidden middle 1, 40 paired 40, extra 40, which makes the outcome of another 40.
46. Inner hidden middle 2, 41 paired 41, extra 41, which makes the outcome of another 41.
47. Inner hidden middle 3, 42 paired 42, extra 42, which makes the outcome of another 42.
48. Inner hidden middle 4, 43 paired 43, extra 43, which makes the outcome of another 43.
49. Inner hidden middle 5, 44 paired 44, extra 44, which makes the outcome of another 44.
50. Inner hidden middle 6, 45 paired 45, extra 45, which makes the outcome of another 45.
51. Inner hidden middle 7, 46 paired 46, extra 46, which makes the outcome of another 46.
52. Inner hidden middle 8, 47 paired 47, extra 47, which makes the outcome of another 47.
53. Inner hidden middle 9, 48 paired 48, extra 48, which makes the outcome of another 48.
54. Inner hidden middle 10, 49 paired 49, extra 49, which makes the outcome of another 49.
55. Inner hidden middle 11, 50 paired 50, extra 50, which makes the outcome of another 50.
56. Inner hidden middle 12, 51 paired 51, extra 51, which makes the outcome of another 51.
57. Inner hidden middle 13, 52 paired 52, extra 52, which makes the outcome of another 52.
58. Inner hidden middle 14, 53 paired 53, extra 53, which makes the outcome of another 53.
59. Inner hidden middle 15, 54 paired 54, extra 54, which makes the outcome of another 54.
60. Inner hidden middle 16, 55 paired 55, extra 55, which makes the outcome of another 55.
61. Inner hidden middle 17, 56 paired 56, extra 56, which makes the outcome of another 56.
62. Inner hidden middle 18, 57 paired 57, extra 57, which makes the outcome of another 57.
63. Inner hidden middle 19, 58 paired 58, extra 58, which makes the outcome of another 58.
64. Inner hidden middle 20, 59 paired 59, extra 59, which makes the outcome of another 59.

65. Inner hidden middle 21, 60 paired 60, extra 60, which makes the outcome of another 60.
66. Inner hidden middle 22, 61 paired 61, extra 61, which makes the outcome of another 61.
67. Inner hidden middle 23, 62 paired 62, extra 62, which makes the outcome of another 62.
68. Inner hidden middle 24, 63 paired 63, extra 63, which makes the outcome of another 63.
69. Inner hidden middle 25, 64 paired 64, extra 64, which makes the outcome of another 64.
70. Inner hidden middle 26, 65 paired 65, extra 65, which makes the outcome of another 65.
71. Inner hidden middle 27, 66 paired 66, extra 66, which makes the outcome of another 66.
72. Inner hidden middle 28, 67 paired 67, extra 67, which makes the outcome of another 67.
73. Inner hidden middle 29, 68 paired 68, extra 68, which makes the outcome of another 68.
74. Inner hidden middle 30, 69 paired 69, extra 69, which makes the outcome of another 69.
75. Inner hidden middle 31, 70 paired 70, extra 70, which makes the outcome of another 70.
76. Inner hidden middle 32, 71 paired 71, extra 71, which makes the outcome of another 71.
77. Inner hidden middle 33, 72 paired 72, extra 72, which makes the outcome of another 72.
78. Inner hidden middle 34, 73 paired 73, extra 73, which makes the outcome of another 73.
79. Inner hidden middle 35, 74 paired 74, extra 74, which makes the outcome of another 74.
80. Inner hidden middle 36, 75 paired 75, extra 75, which makes the outcome of another 75.
81. Inner hidden outer 1, 76 paired 76, extra 76, which makes the outcome of another 76.
82. Inner hidden outer 2, 77 paired 77, extra 77, which makes the outcome of another 77.
83. Inner hidden outer 3, 78 paired 78, extra 78, which makes the outcome of another 78.
84. Inner hidden outer 4, 79 paired 79, extra 79, which makes the outcome of another 79.

85. Inner hidden outer 5, 80 paired 80, extra 80, which makes the outcome of another 80.
86. Inner hidden outer 6, 81 paired 81, extra 81, which makes the outcome of another 81.
87. Inner hidden outer 7, 82 paired 82, extra 82, which makes the outcome of another 82.
88. Inner hidden outer 8, 83 paired 83, extra 83, which makes the outcome of another 83.
89. Inner hidden outer 9, 84 paired 84, extra 84, which makes the outcome of another 84.
90. Inner hidden outer 10, 85 paired 85, extra 85, which makes the outcome of another 85.
91. Inner hidden outer 11, 86 paired 86, extra 86, which makes the outcome of another 86.
92. Inner hidden outer 12, 87 paired 87, extra 87, which makes the outcome of another 87.
93. Inner hidden outer 13, 88 paired 88, extra 88, which makes the outcome of another 88.
94. Inner hidden outer 14, 89 paired 89, extra 89, which makes the outcome of another 89.
95. Inner hidden outer 15, 90 paired 90, extra 90, which makes the outcome of another 90.
96. Inner hidden outer 16, 91 paired 91, extra 91, which makes the outcome of another 91.
97. Inner hidden outer 17, 92 paired 92, extra 92, which makes the outcome of another 92.
98. Inner hidden outer 18, 93 paired 93, extra 93, which makes the outcome of another 93.
99. Inner hidden outer 19, 94 paired 94, extra 94, which makes the outcome of another 94.
100. Inner hidden outer 20, 95 paired 95, extra 95, which makes the outcome of another 95.
101. Inner hidden outer 21, 96 paired 96, extra 96, which makes the outcome of another 96.
102. Inner hidden outer 22, 97 paired 97, extra 97, which makes the outcome of another 97.
103. Inner hidden outer 23, 98 paired 98, extra 98, which makes the outcome of another 98.
104. Inner hidden outer 24, 99 paired 99, extra 99, which makes the outcome of another 99.

105. Inner hidden outer 25, 100 paired 100, extra 100, which makes the outcome of another 100.
106. Inner hidden outer 26, 101 paired 101, extra 101, which makes the outcome of another 101.
107. Inner hidden outer 27, 102 paired 102, extra 102, which makes the outcome of another 102.
108. Inner hidden outer 28, 103 paired 103, extra 103, which makes the outcome of another 103.
109. Inner hidden outer 29, 104 paired 104, extra 104, which makes the outcome of another 104.
110. Inner hidden outer 30, 105 paired 105, extra 105, which makes the outcome of another 105.
111. Inner hidden outer 31, 106 paired 106, extra 106, which makes the outcome of another 106.
112. Inner hidden outer 32, 107 paired 107, extra 107, which makes the outcome of another 107.
113. Inner hidden outer 33, 108 paired 108, extra 108, which makes the outcome of another 108.
114. Inner hidden outer 34, 109 paired 109, extra 109, which makes the outcome of another 109.
115. Inner hidden outer 35, 110 paired 110, extra 110, which makes the outcome of another 110.
116. Inner hidden outer 36, 111 paired 111, extra 111, which makes the outcome of another 111.
117. Inner seen inner 1, 112 paired 112, extra 112, which makes the outcome of another 112.
118. Inner seen inner 2, 113 paired 113, extra 113, which makes the outcome of another 113.
119. Inner seen inner 3, 114 paired 114, extra 114, which makes the outcome of another 114.
120. Inner seen inner 4, 115 paired 115, extra 115, which makes the outcome of another 115.
121. Inner seen inner 5, 116 paired 116, extra 116, which makes the outcome of another 116.
122. Inner seen inner 6, 117 paired 117, extra 117, which makes the outcome of another 117.
123. Inner seen inner 7, 118 paired 118, extra 118, which makes the outcome of another 118.
124. Inner seen inner 8, 119 paired 119, extra 119, which makes the outcome of another 119.

125. Inner seen inner 9, 120 paired 120, extra 120, which makes the outcome of another 120.
126. Inner seen inner 10, 121 paired 121, extra 121, which makes the outcome of another 121.
127. Inner seen inner 11, 122 paired 122, extra 122, which makes the outcome of another 122.
128. Inner seen inner 12, 123 paired 123, extra 123, which makes the outcome of another 123.
129. Inner seen inner 13, 124 paired 124, extra 124, which makes the outcome of another 124.
130. Inner seen inner 14, 125 paired 125, extra 125, which makes the outcome of another 125.
131. Inner seen inner 15, 126 paired 126, extra 126, which makes the outcome of another 126.
132. Inner seen inner 16, 127 paired 127, extra 127, which makes the outcome of another 127.
133. Inner seen inner 17, 128 paired 128, extra 128, which makes the outcome of another 128.
134. Inner seen inner 18, 129 paired 129, extra 129, which makes the outcome of another 129.
135. Inner seen inner 19, 130 paired 130, extra 130, which makes the outcome of another 130.
136. Inner seen inner 20, 131 paired 131, extra 131, which makes the outcome of another 131.
137. Inner seen inner 21, 132 paired 132, extra 132, which makes the outcome of another 132.
138. Inner seen inner 22, 133 paired 133, extra 133, which makes the outcome of another 133.
139. Inner seen inner 23, 134 paired 134, extra 134, which makes the outcome of another 134.
140. Inner seen inner 24, 135 paired 135, extra 135, which makes the outcome of another 135.
141. Inner seen inner 25, 136 paired 136, extra 136, which makes the outcome of another 136.
142. Inner seen inner 26, 137 paired 137, extra 137, which makes the outcome of another 137.
143. Inner seen inner 27, 138 paired 138, extra 138, which makes the outcome of another 138.
144. Inner seen inner 29, 139 paired 139, extra 139, which makes the outcome of another 139.

145. Inner seen inner 30, 140 paired 140, extra 140, which makes the outcome of another 140.
146. Inner seen inner 31, 141 paired 141, extra 141, which makes the outcome of another 141.
147. Inner seen inner 32, 142 paired 142, extra 142, which makes the outcome of another 142.
148. Inner seen inner 33, 143 paired 143, extra 143, which makes the outcome of another 143.
149. Inner seen inner 34, 144 paired 144, extra 144, which makes the outcome of another 144.
150. Inner seen inner 35, 145 paired 145, extra 145, which makes the outcome of another 145.
151. Inner seen inner 36, 146 paired 146, extra 146, which makes the outcome of another 146.
152. Inner seen middle 1, 147 paired 147, extra 147, which makes the outcome of another 147.
153. Inner seen middle 2, 148 paired 148, extra 148, which makes the outcome of another 148.
154. Inner seen middle 3, 149 paired 149, extra 149, which makes the outcome of another 149.
155. Inner seen middle 4, 150 paired 150, extra 150, which makes the outcome of another 150.
156. Inner seen middle 5, 151 paired 151, extra 151, which makes the outcome of another 151.
157. Inner seen middle 6, 152 paired 152, extra 152, which makes the outcome of another 152.
158. Inner seen middle 7, 153 paired 153, extra 153, which makes the outcome of another 153.
159. Inner seen middle 8, 154 paired 154, extra 154, which makes the outcome of another 154.
160. Inner seen middle 9, 155 paired 155, extra 155, which makes the outcome of another 155.
161. Inner seen middle 10, 156 paired 156, extra 156, which makes the outcome of another 156.
162. Inner seen middle 11, 157 paired 157, extra 157, which makes the outcome of another 157.
163. Inner seen middle 12, 158 paired 158, extra 158, which makes the outcome of another 158.
164. Inner seen middle 13, 159 paired 159, extra 159, which makes the outcome of another 159.

165. Inner seen middle 14, 160 paired 160, extra 160, which makes the outcome of another 160.
166. Inner seen middle 15, 161 paired 161, extra 161, which makes the outcome of another 161.
167. Inner seen middle 16, 162 paired 162, extra 162, which makes the outcome of another 162.
168. Inner seen middle 17, 163 paired 163, extra 163, which makes the outcome of another 163.
169. Inner seen middle 18, 164 paired 164, extra 164, which makes the outcome of another 164.
170. Inner seen middle 19, 165 paired 165, extra 165, which makes the outcome of another 165.
171. Inner seen middle 20, 166 paired 166, extra 166, which makes the outcome of another 166.
172. Inner seen middle 21, 167 paired 167, extra 167, which makes the outcome of another 167.
173. Inner seen middle 22, 168 paired 168, extra 168, which makes the outcome of another 168.
174. Inner seen middle 23, 169 paired 169, extra 169, which makes the outcome of another 169.
175. Inner seen middle 24, 170 paired 170, extra 170, which makes the outcome of another 170.
176. Inner seen middle 25, 171 paired 171, extra 171, which makes the outcome of another 171.
177. Inner seen middle 26, 172 paired 172, extra 172, which makes the outcome of another 172.
178. Inner seen middle 27, 173 paired 173, extra 173, which makes the outcome of another 173.
179. Inner seen middle 28, 174 paired 174, extra 174, which makes the outcome of another 174.
180. Inner seen middle 29, 175 paired 175, extra 175, which makes the outcome of another 175.
181. Inner seen middle 30, 176 paired 176, extra 176, which makes the outcome of another 176.
182. Inner seen middle 31, 177 paired 177, extra 177, which makes the outcome of another 177.
183. Inner seen middle 32, 178 paired 178, extra 178, which makes the outcome of another 178.
184. Inner seen middle 33, 179 paired 179, extra 179, which makes the outcome of another 179.

185. Inner seen middle 34, 180 paired 180, extra 180, which makes the outcome of another 180.
186. Inner seen middle 35, 181 paired 181, extra 181, which makes the outcome of another 181.
187. Inner seen middle 36, 182 paired 182, extra 182, which makes the outcome of another 182.
188. Inner seen outer 1, 183 paired 183, extra 183, which makes the outcome of another 183.
189. Inner seen outer 2, 184 paired 184, extra 184, which makes the outcome of another 184.
190. Inner seen outer 3, 185 paired 185, extra 185, which makes the outcome of another 185.
191. Inner seen outer 4, 186 paired 186, extra 186, which makes the outcome of another 186.
192. Inner seen outer 5, 187 paired 187, extra 187, which makes the outcome of another 187.
193. Inner seen outer 6, 188 paired 188, extra 188, which makes the outcome of another 188.
194. Inner seen outer 7, 189 paired 189, extra 189, which makes the outcome of another 189.
195. Inner seen outer 8, 190 paired 190, extra 190, which makes the outcome of another 190.
196. Inner seen outer 9, 191 paired 191, extra 191, which makes the outcome of another 191.
197. Inner seen outer 10, 192 paired 192, extra 192, which makes the outcome of another 192.
198. Inner seen outer 11, 193 paired 193, extra 193, which makes the outcome of another 193.
199. Inner seen outer 12, 194 paired 194, extra 194, which makes the outcome of another 194.
200. Inner seen outer 13, 195 paired 195, extra 195, which makes the outcome of another 195.
201. Inner seen outer 14, 196 paired 196, extra 196, which makes the outcome of another 196.
202. Inner seen outer 15, 197 paired 197, extra 197, which makes the outcome of another 197.
203. Inner seen outer 16, 198 paired 198, extra 198, which makes the outcome of another 198.
204. Inner seen outer 17, 199 paired 199, extra 199, which makes the outcome of another 199.

205. Inner seen outer 18, 200 paired 200, extra 200, which makes the outcome of another 200.
206. Inner seen outer 19, 201 paired 201, extra 201, which makes the outcome of another 201.
207. Inner seen outer 20, 202 paired 202, extra 202, which makes the outcome of another 202.
208. Inner seen outer 21, 203 paired 203, extra 203, which makes the outcome of another 203.
209. Inner seen outer 22, 204 paired 204, extra 204, which makes the outcome of another 204.
210. Inner seen outer 23, 205 paired 205, extra 205, which makes the outcome of another 205.
211. Inner seen outer 24, 206 paired 206, extra 206, which makes the outcome of another 206.
212. Inner seen outer 25, 207 paired 207, extra 207, which makes the outcome of another 207.
213. Inner seen outer 26, 208 paired 208, extra 208, which makes the outcome of another 208.
214. Inner seen outer 27, 209 paired 209, extra 209, which makes the outcome of another 209.
215. Inner seen outer 28, 210 paired 210, extra 210, which makes the outcome of another 210.
216. Inner seen outer 29, 211 paired 211, extra 211, which makes the outcome of another 211.
217. Inner seen outer 30, 212 paired 212, extra 212, which makes the outcome of another 212.
218. Inner seen outer 31, 213 paired 213, extra 213, which makes the outcome of another 213.
219. Inner seen outer 32, 214 paired 214, extra 214, which makes the outcome of another 214.
220. Inner seen outer 33, 215 paired 215, extra 215, which makes the outcome of another 215.
221. Inner seen outer 34, 216 paired 216, extra 216, which makes the outcome of another 216.
222. Inner seen outer 35, 217 paired 217, extra 217, which makes the outcome of another 217.
223. Inner seen outer 36, 218 paired 218, extra 218, which makes the outcome of another 218.
224. Middle hidden inner 1, 219 paired 219, extra 219, which makes the outcome of another 219.

225. Middle hidden inner 2, 220 paired 220, extra 220, which makes the outcome of another 220.
226. Middle hidden inner 3, 221 paired 221, extra 221, which makes the outcome of another 221.
227. Middle hidden inner 4, 222 paired 222, extra 222, which makes the outcome of another 222.
228. Middle hidden inner 5, 223 paired 223, extra 223, which makes the outcome of another 223.
229. Middle hidden inner 6, 224 paired 224, extra 224, which makes the outcome of another 224.
230. Middle hidden inner 7, 225 paired 225, extra 225, which makes the outcome of another 225.
231. Middle hidden inner 8, 226 paired 226, extra 226, which makes the outcome of another 226.
232. Middle hidden inner 9, 227 paired 227, extra 227, which makes the outcome of another 227.
233. Middle hidden inner 10, 228 paired 228, extra 228, which makes the outcome of another 228.
234. Middle hidden inner 11, 229 paired 229, extra 229, which makes the outcome of another 229.
235. Middle hidden inner 12, 230 paired 230, extra 230, which makes the outcome of another 230.
236. Middle hidden inner 13, 231 paired 231, extra 231, which makes the outcome of another 231.
237. Middle hidden inner 14, 232 paired 232, extra 232, which makes the outcome of another 232.
238. Middle hidden inner 15, 233 paired 233, extra 233, which makes the outcome of another 233.
239. Middle hidden inner 16, 234 paired 234, extra 234, which makes the outcome of another 234.
240. Middle hidden inner 17, 235 paired 235, extra 235, which makes the outcome of another 235.
241. Middle hidden inner 18, 236 paired 236, extra 236, which makes the outcome of another 236.
242. Middle hidden inner 19, 237 paired 237, extra 237, which makes the outcome of another 237.
243. Middle hidden inner 20, 238 paired 238, extra 238, which makes the outcome of another 238.
244. Middle hidden inner 21, 239 paired 239, extra 239, which makes the outcome of another 239.

245. Middle hidden inner 22, 240 paired 240, extra 240, which makes the outcome of another 240.
246. Middle hidden inner 23, 241 paired 241, extra 241, which makes the outcome of another 241.
247. Middle hidden inner 24, 242 paired 242, extra 242, which makes the outcome of another 242.
248. Middle hidden inner 25, 243 paired 243, extra 243, which makes the outcome of another 243.
249. Middle hidden inner 26, 244 paired 244, extra 244, which makes the outcome of another 244.
250. Middle hidden inner 27, 245 paired 245, extra 245, which makes the outcome of another 245.
251. Middle hidden inner 28, 246 paired 246, extra 246, which makes the outcome of another 246.
252. Middle hidden inner 29, 247 paired 247, extra 247, which makes the outcome of another 247.
253. Middle hidden inner 30, 248 paired 248, extra 248, which makes the outcome of another 248.
254. Middle hidden inner 31, 249 paired 249, extra 249, which makes the outcome of another 249.
255. Middle hidden inner 32, 250 paired 250, extra 250, which makes the outcome of another 250.
256. Middle hidden inner 33, 251 paired 251, extra 251, which makes the outcome of another 251.
257. Middle hidden inner 34, 252 paired 252, extra 252, which makes the outcome of another 252.
258. Middle hidden inner 35, 253 paired 253, extra 253, which makes the outcome of another 253.
259. Middle hidden inner 36, 254 paired 254, extra 254, which makes the outcome of another 254.
260. Middle hidden middle 1, 255 paired 255, extra 255, which makes the outcome of another 255.
261. Middle hidden middle 2, 256 paired 256, extra 256, which makes the outcome of another 256.
262. Middle hidden middle 3, 257 paired 257, extra 257, which makes the outcome of another 257.
263. Middle hidden middle 4, 258 paired 258, extra 258, which makes the outcome of another 258.
264. Middle hidden middle 5, 259 paired 259, extra 259, which makes the outcome of another 259.

265. Middle hidden middle 6, 260 paired 260, extra 260, which makes the outcome of another 260.
266. Middle hidden middle 7, 261 paired 261, extra 261, which makes the outcome of another 261.
267. Middle hidden middle 8, 262 paired 262, extra 262, which makes the outcome of another 262.
268. Middle hidden middle 9, 263 paired 263, extra 263, which makes the outcome of another 263.
269. Middle hidden middle 10, 264 paired 264, extra 264, which makes the outcome of another 264.
270. Middle hidden middle 11, 265 paired 265, extra 265, which makes the outcome of another 265.
271. Middle hidden middle 12, 266 paired 266, extra 266, which makes the outcome of another 266.
272. Middle hidden middle 13, 267 paired 267, extra 267, which makes the outcome of another 267.
273. Middle hidden middle 14, 268 paired 268, extra 268, which makes the outcome of another 268.
274. Middle hidden middle 15, 269 paired 269, extra 269, which makes the outcome of another 269.
275. Middle hidden middle 16, 270 paired 270, extra 270, which makes the outcome of another 270.
276. Middle hidden middle 17, 271 paired 271, extra 271, which makes the outcome of another 271.
277. Middle hidden middle 18, 272 paired 272, extra 272, which makes the outcome of another 272.
278. Middle hidden middle 19, 273 paired 273, extra 273, which makes the outcome of another 273.
279. Middle hidden middle 20, 274 paired 274, extra 274, which makes the outcome of another 274.
280. Middle hidden middle 21, 275 paired 275, extra 275, which makes the outcome of another 275.
281. Middle hidden middle 22, 276 paired 276, extra 276, which makes the outcome of another 276.
282. Middle hidden middle 23, 277 paired 277, extra 277, which makes the outcome of another 277.
283. Middle hidden middle 24, 278 paired 278, extra 278, which makes the outcome of another 278.
284. Middle hidden middle 25, 279 paired 279, extra 279, which makes the outcome of another 279.

285. Middle hidden middle 26, 280 paired 280, extra 280, which makes the outcome of another 280.
286. Middle hidden middle 27, 281 paired 281, extra 281, which makes the outcome of another 281.
287. Middle hidden middle 28, 282 paired 282, extra 282, which makes the outcome of another 282.
288. Middle hidden middle 29, 283 paired 283, extra 283, which makes the outcome of another 283.
289. Middle hidden middle 30, 284 paired 284, extra 284, which makes the outcome of another 284.
290. Middle hidden middle 31, 285 paired 285, extra 285, which makes the outcome of another 285.
291. Middle hidden middle 32, 286 paired 286, extra 286, which makes the outcome of another 286.
292. Middle hidden middle 33, 287 paired 287, extra 287, which makes the outcome of another 287.
293. Middle hidden middle 34, 288 paired 288, extra 288, which makes the outcome of another 288.
294. Middle hidden middle 35, 289 paired 289, extra 289, which makes the outcome of another 289.
295. Middle hidden middle 36, 290 paired 290, extra 290, which makes the outcome of another 290.
296. Middle hidden outer 1, 291 paired 291, extra 291, which makes the outcome of another 291.
297. Middle hidden outer 2, 292 paired 292, extra 292, which makes the outcome of another 292.
298. Middle hidden outer 3, 293 paired 293, extra 293, which makes the outcome of another 293.
299. Middle hidden outer 4, 294 paired 294, extra 294, which makes the outcome of another 294.
300. Middle hidden outer 5, 295 paired 295, extra 295, which makes the outcome of another 295.
301. Middle hidden outer 6, 296 paired 296, extra 296, which makes the outcome of another 296.
302. Middle hidden outer 7, 297 paired 297, extra 297, which makes the outcome of another 297.
303. Middle hidden outer 8, 298 paired 298, extra 298, which makes the outcome of another 298.
304. Middle hidden outer 9, 299 paired 299, extra 299, which makes the outcome of another 299.

305. Middle hidden outer 10, 300 paired 300, extra 300, which makes the outcome of another 300.
306. Middle hidden outer 11, 301 paired 301, extra 301, which makes the outcome of another 301.
307. Middle hidden outer 12, 302 paired 302, extra 302, which makes the outcome of another 302.
308. Middle hidden outer 13, 303 paired 303, extra 303, which makes the outcome of another 303.
309. Middle hidden outer 14, 304 paired 304, extra 304, which makes the outcome of another 304.
310. Middle hidden outer 15, 305 paired 305, extra 305, which makes the outcome of another 305.
311. Middle hidden outer 16, 306 paired 306, extra 306, which makes the outcome of another 306.
312. Middle hidden outer 17, 307 paired 307, extra 307, which makes the outcome of another 307.
313. Middle hidden outer 18, 308 paired 308, extra 308, which makes the outcome of another 308.
314. Middle hidden outer 19, 309 paired 309, extra 309, which makes the outcome of another 309.
315. Middle hidden outer 20, 310 paired 310, extra 310, which makes the outcome of another 310.
316. Middle hidden outer 21, 311 paired 311, extra 311, which makes the outcome of another 311.
317. Middle hidden outer 22, 312 paired 312, extra 312, which makes the outcome of another 312.
318. Middle hidden outer 23, 313 paired 313, extra 313, which makes the outcome of another 313.
319. Middle hidden outer 24, 314 paired 314, extra 314, which makes the outcome of another 314.
320. Middle hidden outer 25, 315 paired 315, extra 315, which makes the outcome of another 315.
321. Middle hidden outer 26, 316 paired 316, extra 316, which makes the outcome of another 316.
322. Middle hidden outer 27, 317 paired 317, extra 317, which makes the outcome of another 317.
323. Middle hidden outer 28, 318 paired 318, extra 318, which makes the outcome of another 318.
324. Middle hidden outer 29, 319 paired 319, extra 319, which makes the outcome of another 319.

325. Middle hidden outer 30, 320 paired 320, extra 320, which makes the outcome of another 320.
326. Middle hidden outer 31, 321 paired 321, extra 321, which makes the outcome of another 321.
327. Middle hidden outer 32, 322 paired 322, extra 322, which makes the outcome of another 322.
328. Middle hidden outer 33, 323 paired 323, extra 323, which makes the outcome of another 323.
329. Middle hidden outer 34, 324 paired 324, extra 324, which makes the outcome of another 324.
330. Middle hidden outer 35, 325 paired 325, extra 325, which makes the outcome of another 325.
331. Middle hidden outer 36, 326 paired 326, extra 326, which makes the outcome of another 326.
332. Middle seen inner 1, 327 paired 327, extra 327, which makes the outcome of another 327.
333. Middle seen inner 2, 328 paired 328, extra 328, which makes the outcome of another 328.
334. Middle seen inner 3, 329 paired 329, extra 329, which makes the outcome of another 329.
335. Middle seen inner 4, 330 paired 330, extra 330, which makes the outcome of another 330.
336. Middle seen inner 5, 331 paired 331, extra 331, which makes the outcome of another 331.
337. Middle seen inner 6, 332 paired 332, extra 332, which makes the outcome of another 332.
338. Middle seen inner 7, 333 paired 333, extra 333, which makes the outcome of another 333.
339. Middle seen inner 8, 334 paired 334, extra 334, which makes the outcome of another 334.
340. Middle seen inner 9, 335 paired 335, extra 335, which makes the outcome of another 335.
341. Middle seen inner 10, 336 paired 336, extra 336, which makes the outcome of another 336.
342. Middle seen inner 11, 337 paired 337, extra 337, which makes the outcome of another 337.
343. Middle seen inner 12, 338 paired 338, extra 338, which makes the outcome of another 338.
344. Middle seen inner 13, 339 paired 339, extra 339, which makes the outcome of another 339.

345. Middle seen inner 14, 340 paired 340, extra 340, which makes the outcome of another 340.
346. Middle seen inner 15, 341 paired 341, extra 341, which makes the outcome of another 341.
347. Middle seen inner 16, 342 paired 342, extra 342, which makes the outcome of another 342.
348. Middle seen inner 17, 343 paired 343, extra 343, which makes the outcome of another 343.
349. Middle seen inner 18, 344 paired 344, extra 344, which makes the outcome of another 344.
350. Middle seen inner 19, 345 paired 345, extra 345, which makes the outcome of another 345.
351. Middle seen inner 20, 346 paired 346, extra 346, which makes the outcome of another 346.
352. Middle seen inner 21, 347 paired 347, extra 347, which makes the outcome of another 347.
353. Middle seen inner 22, 348 paired 348, extra 348, which makes the outcome of another 348.
354. Middle seen inner 23, 349 paired 349, extra 349, which makes the outcome of another 349.
355. Middle seen inner 24, 350 paired 350, extra 350, which makes the outcome of another 350.
356. Middle seen inner 25, 351 paired 351, extra 351, which makes the outcome of another 351.
357. Middle seen inner 26, 352 paired 352, extra 352, which makes the outcome of another 352.
358. Middle seen inner 27, 353 paired 353, extra 353, which makes the outcome of another 353.
359. Middle seen inner 28, 354 paired 354, extra 354, which makes the outcome of another 354.
360. Middle seen inner 29, 355 paired 355, extra 355, which makes the outcome of another 355.
361. Middle seen inner 30, 356 paired 356, extra 356, which makes the outcome of another 356.
362. Middle seen inner 31, 357 paired 357, extra 357, which makes the outcome of another 357.
363. Middle seen inner 32, 358 paired 358, extra 358, which makes the outcome of another 358.
364. Middle seen inner 33, 359 paired 359, extra 359, which makes the outcome of another 359.

365. Middle seen inner 34, 360 paired 360, extra 360, which makes the outcome of another 360.
366. Middle seen inner 35, 361 paired 361, extra 361, which makes the outcome of another 361.
367. Middle seen inner 36, 362 paired 362, extra 362, which makes the outcome of another 362.
368. Middle seen middle 1, 363 paired 363, extra 363, which makes the outcome of another 363.
369. Middle seen middle 2, 364 paired 364, extra 364, which makes the outcome of another 364.
370. Middle seen middle 3, 365 paired 365, extra 365, which makes the outcome of another 365.
371. Middle seen middle 4, 366 paired 366, extra 366, which makes the outcome of another 366.
372. Middle seen middle 5, 367 paired 367, extra 367, which makes the outcome of another 367.
373. Middle seen middle 6, 368 paired 368, extra 368, which makes the outcome of another 368.
374. Middle seen middle 7, 369 paired 369, extra 369, which makes the outcome of another 369.
375. Middle seen middle 8, 370 paired 370, extra 370, which makes the outcome of another 370.
376. Middle seen middle 9, 371 paired 371, extra 371, which makes the outcome of another 371.
377. Middle seen middle 10, 372 paired 372, extra 372, which makes the outcome of another 372.
378. Middle seen middle 11, 373 paired 373, extra 373, which makes the outcome of another 373.
379. Middle seen middle 12, 374 paired 374, extra 374, which makes the outcome of another 374.
380. Middle seen middle 13, 375 paired 375, extra 375, which makes the outcome of another 375.
381. Middle seen middle 14, 376 paired 376, extra 376, which makes the outcome of another 376.
382. Middle seen middle 15, 377 paired 377, extra 377, which makes the outcome of another 377.
383. Middle seen middle 16, 378 paired 378, extra 378, which makes the outcome of another 378.
384. Middle seen middle 17, 379 paired 379, extra 379, which makes the outcome of another 379.

385. Middle seen middle 18, 380 paired 380, extra 380, which makes the outcome of another 380.
386. Middle seen middle 19, 381 paired 381, extra 381, which makes the outcome of another 381.
387. Middle seen middle 20, 382 paired 382, extra 382, which makes the outcome of another 382.
388. Middle seen middle 21, 383 paired 383, extra 383, which makes the outcome of another 383.
389. Middle seen middle 22, 384 paired 384, extra 384, which makes the outcome of another 384.
390. Middle seen middle 23, 385 paired 385, extra 385, which makes the outcome of another 385.
391. Middle seen middle 24, 386 paired 386, extra 386, which makes the outcome of another 386.
392. Middle seen middle 25, 387 paired 387, extra 387, which makes the outcome of another 387.
393. Middle seen middle 26, 388 paired 388, extra 388, which makes the outcome of another 388.
394. Middle seen middle 27, 389 paired 389, extra 389, which makes the outcome of another 389.
395. Middle seen middle 28, 390 paired 390, extra 390, which makes the outcome of another 390.
396. Middle seen middle 29, 391 paired 391, extra 391, which makes the outcome of another 391.
397. Middle seen middle 30, 392 paired 392, extra 392, which makes the outcome of another 392.
398. Middle seen middle 31, 393 paired 393, extra 393, which makes the outcome of another 393.
399. Middle seen middle 32, 394 paired 394, extra 394, which makes the outcome of another 394.
400. Middle seen middle 33, 395 paired 395, extra 395, which makes the outcome of another 395.
401. Middle seen middle 34, 396 paired 396, extra 396, which makes the outcome of another 396.
402. Middle seen middle 35, 397 paired 397, extra 397, which makes the outcome of another 397.
403. Middle seen middle 36, 398 paired 398, extra 398, which makes the outcome of another 398.
404. Middle seen outer 1, 399 paired 399, extra 399, which makes the outcome of another 399.

405. Middle seen outer 2, 400 paired 400, extra 400, which makes the outcome of another 400.
406. Middle seen outer 3, 401 paired 401, extra 401, which makes the outcome of another 401.
407. Middle seen outer 4, 402 paired 402, extra 402, which makes the outcome of another 402.
408. Middle seen outer 5, 403 paired 403, extra 403, which makes the outcome of another 403.
409. Middle seen outer 6, 404 paired 404, extra 404, which makes the outcome of another 404.
410. Middle seen outer 7, 405 paired 405, extra 405, which makes the outcome of another 405.
411. Middle seen outer 8, 406 paired 406, extra 406, which makes the outcome of another 406.
412. Middle seen outer 9, 407 paired 407, extra 407, which makes the outcome of another 407.
413. Middle seen outer 10, 408 paired 408, extra 408, which makes the outcome of another 408.
414. Middle seen outer 11, 409 paired 409, extra 409, which makes the outcome of another 409.
415. Middle seen outer 12, 410 paired 410, extra 410, which makes the outcome of another 410.
416. Middle seen outer 13, 411 paired 411, extra 411, which makes the outcome of another 411.
417. Middle seen outer 14, 412 paired 412, extra 412, which makes the outcome of another 412.
418. Middle seen outer 15, 413 paired 413, extra 413, which makes the outcome of another 413.
419. Middle seen outer 16, 414 paired 414, extra 414, which makes the outcome of another 414.
420. Middle seen outer 17, 415 paired 415, extra 415, which makes the outcome of another 415.
421. Middle seen outer 18, 416 paired 416, extra 416, which makes the outcome of another 416.
422. Middle seen outer 19, 417 paired 417, extra 417, which makes the outcome of another 417.
423. Middle seen outer 20, 418 paired 418, extra 418, which makes the outcome of another 418.
424. Middle seen outer 21, 419 paired 419, extra 419, which makes the outcome of another 419.

425. Middle seen outer 22, 420 paired 420, extra 420, which makes the outcome of another 420.
426. Middle seen outer 23, 421 paired 421, extra 421, which makes the outcome of another 421.
427. Middle seen outer 24, 422 paired 422, extra 422, which makes the outcome of another 422.
428. Middle seen outer 25, 423 paired 423, extra 423, which makes the outcome of another 423.
429. Middle seen outer 26, 424 paired 424, extra 424, which makes the outcome of another 424.
430. Middle seen outer 27, 425 paired 425, extra 425, which makes the outcome of another 425.
431. Middle seen outer 28, 426 paired 426, extra 426, which makes the outcome of another 426.
432. Middle seen outer 29, 427 paired 427, extra 427, which makes the outcome of another 427.
433. Middle seen outer 30, 428 paired 428, extra 428, which makes the outcome of another 428.
434. Middle seen outer 31, 429 paired 429, extra 429, which makes the outcome of another 429.
435. Middle seen outer 32, 430 paired 430, extra 430, which makes the outcome of another 430.
436. Middle seen outer 33, 431 paired 431, extra 431, which makes the outcome of another 431.
437. Middle seen outer 34, 432 paired 432, extra 432, which makes the outcome of another 432.
438. Middle seen outer 35, 433 paired 433, extra 433, which makes the outcome of another 433.
439. Middle seen outer 36, 434 paired 434, extra 434, which makes the outcome of another 434.
440. Outer hidden inner 1, 435 paired 435, extra 435, which makes the outcome of another 435.
441. Outer hidden inner 2, 436 paired 436, extra 436, which makes the outcome of another 436.
442. Outer hidden inner 3, 437 paired 437, extra 437, which makes the outcome of another 437.
443. Outer hidden inner 4, 438 paired 438, extra 438, which makes the outcome of another 438.
444. Outer hidden inner 5, 439 paired 439, extra 439, which makes the outcome of another 439.

445. Outer hidden inner 6, 440 paired 440, extra 440, which makes the outcome of another 440.
446. Outer hidden inner 7, 441 paired 441, extra 441, which makes the outcome of another 441.
447. Outer hidden inner 8, 442 paired 442, extra 442, which makes the outcome of another 442.
448. Outer hidden inner 9, 443 paired 443, extra 443, which makes the outcome of another 443.
449. Outer hidden inner 10, 444 paired 444, extra 444, which makes the outcome of another 444.
450. Outer hidden inner 11, 445 paired 445, extra 445, which makes the outcome of another 445.
451. Outer hidden inner 12, 446 paired 446, extra 446, which makes the outcome of another 446.
452. Outer hidden inner 13, 447 paired 447, extra 447, which makes the outcome of another 447.
453. Outer hidden inner 14, 448 paired 448, extra 448, which makes the outcome of another 448.
454. Outer hidden inner 15, 449 paired 449, extra 449, which makes the outcome of another 449.
455. Outer hidden inner 16, 450 paired 450, extra 450, which makes the outcome of another 450.
456. Outer hidden inner 17, 451 paired 451, extra 451, which makes the outcome of another 451.
457. Outer hidden inner 18, 452 paired 452, extra 452, which makes the outcome of another 452.
458. Outer hidden inner 19, 453 paired 453, extra 453, which makes the outcome of another 453.
459. Outer hidden inner 20, 454 paired 454, extra 454, which makes the outcome of another 454.
460. Outer hidden inner 21, 455 paired 455, extra 455, which makes the outcome of another 455.
461. Outer hidden inner 22, 456 paired 456, extra 456, which makes the outcome of another 456.
462. Outer hidden inner 23, 457 paired 457, extra 457, which makes the outcome of another 457.
463. Outer hidden inner 24, 458 paired 458, extra 458, which makes the outcome of another 458.
464. Outer hidden inner 25, 459 paired 459, extra 459, which makes the outcome of another 459.

465. Outer hidden inner 26, 460 paired 460, extra 460, which makes the outcome of another 460.
466. Outer hidden inner 27, 461 paired 461, extra 461, which makes the outcome of another 461.
467. Outer hidden inner 28, 462 paired 462, extra 462, which makes the outcome of another 462.
468. Outer hidden inner 29, 463 paired 463, extra 463, which makes the outcome of another 463.
469. Outer hidden inner 30, 464 paired 464, extra 464, which makes the outcome of another 464.
470. Outer hidden inner 31, 465 paired 465, extra 465, which makes the outcome of another 465.
471. Outer hidden inner 32, 466 paired 466, extra 466, which makes the outcome of another 466.
472. Outer hidden inner 33, 467 paired 467, extra 467, which makes the outcome of another 467.
473. Outer hidden inner 34, 468 paired 468, extra 468, which makes the outcome of another 468.
474. Outer hidden inner 35, 469 paired 469, extra 469, which makes the outcome of another 469.
475. Outer hidden inner 36, 470 paired 470, extra 470, which makes the outcome of another 470.
476. Outer hidden middle 1, 471 paired 471, extra 471, which makes the outcome of another 471.
477. Outer hidden middle 2, 472 paired 472, extra 472, which makes the outcome of another 472.
478. Outer hidden middle 3, 473 paired 473, extra 473, which makes the outcome of another 473.
479. Outer hidden middle 4, 474 paired 474, extra 474, which makes the outcome of another 474.
480. Outer hidden middle 5, 475 paired 475, extra 475, which makes the outcome of another 475.
481. Outer hidden middle 6, 476 paired 476, extra 476, which makes the outcome of another 476.
482. Outer hidden middle 7, 477 paired 477, extra 477, which makes the outcome of another 477.
483. Outer hidden middle 8, 478 paired 478, extra 478, which makes the outcome of another 478.
484. Outer hidden middle 9, 479 paired 479, extra 479, which makes the outcome of another 479.

485. Outer hidden middle 10, 480 paired 480, extra 480, which makes the outcome of another 480.
486. Outer hidden middle 11, 481 paired 481, extra 481, which makes the outcome of another 481.
487. Outer hidden middle 12, 482 paired 482, extra 482, which makes the outcome of another 482.
488. Outer hidden middle 13, 483 paired 483, extra 483, which makes the outcome of another 483.
489. Outer hidden middle 14, 484 paired 484, extra 484, which makes the outcome of another 484.
490. Outer hidden middle 15, 485 paired 485, extra 485, which makes the outcome of another 485.
491. Outer hidden middle 16, 486 paired 486, extra 486, which makes the outcome of another 486.
492. Outer hidden middle 17, 487 paired 487, extra 487, which makes the outcome of another 487.
493. Outer hidden middle 18, 488 paired 488, extra 488, which makes the outcome of another 488.
494. Outer hidden middle 19, 489 paired 489, extra 489, which makes the outcome of another 489.
495. Outer hidden middle 20, 490 paired 490, extra 490, which makes the outcome of another 490.
496. Outer hidden middle 21, 491 paired 491, extra 491, which makes the outcome of another 491.
497. Outer hidden middle 22, 492 paired 492, extra 492, which makes the outcome of another 492.
498. Outer hidden middle 23, 493 paired 493, extra 493, which makes the outcome of another 493.
499. Outer hidden middle 24, 494 paired 494, extra 494, which makes the outcome of another 494.
500. Outer hidden middle 25, 495 paired 495, extra 495, which makes the outcome of another 495.
501. Outer hidden middle 26, 496 paired 496, extra 496, which makes the outcome of another 496.
502. Outer hidden middle 27, 497 paired 497, extra 497, which makes the outcome of another 497.
503. Outer hidden middle 28, 498 paired 498, extra 498, which makes the outcome of another 498.
504. Outer hidden middle 29, 499 paired 499, extra 499, which makes the outcome of another 499.

505. Outer hidden middle 30, 500 paired 500, extra 500, which makes the outcome of another 500.
506. Outer hidden middle 31, 501 paired 501, extra 501, which makes the outcome of another 501.
507. Outer hidden middle 32, 502 paired 502, extra 502, which makes the outcome of another 502.
508. Outer hidden middle 33, 503 paired 503, extra 503, which makes the outcome of another 503.
509. Outer hidden middle 34, 504 paired 504, extra 504, which makes the outcome of another 504.
510. Outer hidden middle 35, 505 paired 505, extra 505, which makes the outcome of another 505.
511. Outer hidden middle 36, 506 paired 506, extra 506, which makes the outcome of another 506.
512. Outer hidden outer 1, 507 paired 507, extra 507, which makes the outcome of another 507.
513. Outer hidden outer 2, 508 paired 508, extra 508, which makes the outcome of another 508.
514. Outer hidden outer 3, 509 paired 509, extra 509, which makes the outcome of another 509.
515. Outer hidden outer 4, 510 paired 510, extra 510, which makes the outcome of another 510.
516. Outer hidden outer 5, 511 paired 511, extra 511, which makes the outcome of another 511.
517. Outer hidden outer 6, 512 paired 512, extra 512, which makes the outcome of another 512.
518. Outer hidden outer 7, 513 paired 513, extra 513, which makes the outcome of another 513.
519. Outer hidden outer 8, 514 paired 514, extra 514, which makes the outcome of another 514.
520. Outer hidden outer 9, 515 paired 515, extra 515, which makes the outcome of another 515.
521. Outer hidden outer 10, 516 paired 516, extra 516, which makes the outcome of another 516.
522. Outer hidden outer 11, 517 paired 517, extra 517, which makes the outcome of another 517.
523. Outer hidden outer 12, 518 paired 518, extra 518, which makes the outcome of another 518.
524. Outer hidden outer 13, 519 paired 519, extra 519, which makes the outcome of another 519.

525. Outer hidden outer 14, 520 paired 520, extra 520, which makes the outcome of another 520.
526. Outer hidden outer 15, 521 paired 521, extra 521, which makes the outcome of another 521.
527. Outer hidden outer 16, 522 paired 522, extra 522, which makes the outcome of another 522.
528. Outer hidden outer 17, 523 paired 523, extra 523, which makes the outcome of another 523.
529. Outer hidden outer 18, 524 paired 524, extra 524, which makes the outcome of another 524.
530. Outer hidden outer 19, 525 paired 525, extra 525, which makes the outcome of another 525.
531. Outer hidden outer 20, 526 paired 526, extra 526, which makes the outcome of another 526.
532. Outer hidden outer 21, 527 paired 527, extra 527, which makes the outcome of another 527.
533. Outer hidden outer 22, 528 paired 528, extra 528, which makes the outcome of another 528.
534. Outer hidden outer 23, 529 paired 529, extra 529, which makes the outcome of another 529.
535. Outer hidden outer 24, 530 paired 530, extra 530, which makes the outcome of another 530.
536. Outer hidden outer 25, 531 paired 531, extra 531, which makes the outcome of another 531.
537. Outer hidden outer 26, 532 paired 532, extra 532, which makes the outcome of another 532.
538. Outer hidden outer 27, 533 paired 533, extra 533, which makes the outcome of another 533.
539. Outer hidden outer 28, 534 paired 534, extra 534, which makes the outcome of another 534.
540. Outer hidden outer 29, 535 paired 535, extra 535, which makes the outcome of another 535.
541. Outer hidden outer 30, 536 paired 536, extra 536, which makes the outcome of another 536.
542. Outer hidden outer 31, 537 paired 537, extra 537, which makes the outcome of another 537.
543. Outer hidden outer 32, 538 paired 538, extra 538, which makes the outcome of another 538.
544. Outer hidden outer 33, 539 paired 539, extra 539, which makes the outcome of another 539.

545. Outer hidden outer 34, 540 paired 540, extra 540, which makes the outcome of another 540.
546. Outer hidden outer 35, 541 paired 541, extra 541, which makes the outcome of another 541.
547. Outer hidden outer 36, 542 paired 542, extra 542, which makes the outcome of another 542.
548. Outer seen inner 1, 543 paired 543, extra 543, which makes the outcome of another 543.
549. Outer seen inner 2, 544 paired 544, extra 544, which makes the outcome of another 544.
550. Outer seen inner 3, 545 paired 545, extra 545, which makes the outcome of another 545.
551. Outer seen inner 4, 546 paired 546, extra 546, which makes the outcome of another 546.
552. Outer seen inner 5, 547 paired 547, extra 547, which makes the outcome of another 547.
553. Outer seen inner 6, 548 paired 548, extra 548, which makes the outcome of another 548.
554. Outer seen inner 7, 549 paired 549, extra 549, which makes the outcome of another 549.
555. Outer seen inner 8, 550 paired 550, extra 550, which makes the outcome of another 550.
556. Outer seen inner 9, 551 paired 551, extra 551, which makes the outcome of another 551.
557. Outer seen inner 10, 552 paired 552, extra 552, which makes the outcome of another 552.
558. Outer seen inner 11, 553 paired 553, extra 553, which makes the outcome of another 553.
559. Outer seen inner 12, 554 paired 554, extra 554, which makes the outcome of another 554.
560. Outer seen inner 13, 555 paired 555, extra 555, which makes the outcome of another 555.
561. Outer seen inner 14, 556 paired 556, extra 556, which makes the outcome of another 556.
562. Outer seen inner 15, 557 paired 557, extra 557, which makes the outcome of another 557.
563. Outer seen inner 16, 558 paired 558, extra 558, which makes the outcome of another 558.
564. Outer seen inner 17, 559 paired 559, extra 559, which makes the outcome of another 559.

565. Outer seen inner 18, 560 paired 560, extra 560, which makes the outcome of another 560.
566. Outer seen inner 19, 561 paired 561, extra 561, which makes the outcome of another 561.
567. Outer seen inner 20, 562 paired 562, extra 562, which makes the outcome of another 562.
568. Outer seen inner 21, 563 paired 563, extra 563, which makes the outcome of another 563.
569. Outer seen inner 22, 564 paired 564, extra 564, which makes the outcome of another 564.
570. Outer seen inner 23, 565 paired 565, extra 565, which makes the outcome of another 565.
571. Outer seen inner 24, 566 paired 566, extra 566, which makes the outcome of another 566.
572. Outer seen inner 25, 567 paired 567, extra 567, which makes the outcome of another 567.
573. Outer seen inner 26, 568 paired 568, extra 568, which makes the outcome of another 568.
574. Outer seen inner 27, 569 paired 569, extra 569, which makes the outcome of another 569.
575. Outer seen inner 28, 570 paired 570, extra 570, which makes the outcome of another 570.
576. Outer seen inner 29, 571 paired 571, extra 571, which makes the outcome of another 571.
577. Outer seen inner 30, 572 paired 572, extra 572, which makes the outcome of another 572.
578. Outer seen inner 31, 573 paired 573, extra 573, which makes the outcome of another 573.
579. Outer seen inner 32, 574 paired 574, extra 574, which makes the outcome of another 574.
580. Outer seen inner 33, 575 paired 575, extra 575, which makes the outcome of another 575.
581. Outer seen inner 34, 576 paired 576, extra 576, which makes the outcome of another 576.
582. Outer seen inner 35, 577 paired 577, extra 577, which makes the outcome of another 577.
583. Outer seen inner 36, 578 paired 578, extra 578, which makes the outcome of another 578.
584. Outer seen middle 1, 579 paired 579, extra 579, which makes the outcome of another 579.

585. Outer seen middle 2, 580 paired 580, extra 580, which makes the outcome of another 580.
586. Outer seen middle 3, 581 paired 581, extra 581, which makes the outcome of another 581.
587. Outer seen middle 4, 582 paired 582, extra 582, which makes the outcome of another 582.
588. Outer seen middle 5, 583 paired 583, extra 583, which makes the outcome of another 583.
589. Outer seen middle 6, 584 paired 584, extra 584, which makes the outcome of another 584.
590. Outer seen middle 7, 585 paired 585, extra 585, which makes the outcome of another 585.
591. Outer seen middle 8, 586 paired 586, extra 586, which makes the outcome of another 586.
592. Outer seen middle 9, 587 paired 587, extra 587, which makes the outcome of another 587.
593. Outer seen middle 10, 588 paired 588, extra 588, which makes the outcome of another 588.
594. Outer seen middle 11, 589 paired 589, extra 589, which makes the outcome of another 589.
595. Outer seen middle 12, 590 paired 590, extra 590, which makes the outcome of another 590.
596. Outer seen middle 13, 591 paired 591, extra 591, which makes the outcome of another 591.
597. Outer seen middle 14, 592 paired 592, extra 592, which makes the outcome of another 592.
598. Outer seen middle 15, 593 paired 593, extra 593, which makes the outcome of another 593.
599. Outer seen middle 16, 594 paired 594, extra 594, which makes the outcome of another 594.
600. Outer seen middle 17, 595 paired 595, extra 595, which makes the outcome of another 595.
601. Outer seen middle 18, 596 paired 596, extra 596, which makes the outcome of another 596.
602. Outer seen middle 19, 597 paired 597, extra 597, which makes the outcome of another 597.
603. Outer seen middle 20, 598 paired 598, extra 598, which makes the outcome of another 598.
604. Outer seen middle 21, 599 paired 599, extra 599, which makes the outcome of another 599.

605. Outer seen middle 22, 600 paired 600, extra 600, which makes the outcome of another 600.
606. Outer seen middle 23, 601 paired 601, extra 601, which makes the outcome of another 601.
607. Outer seen middle 24, 602 paired 602, extra 602, which makes the outcome of another 602.
608. Outer seen middle 25, 603 paired 603, extra 603, which makes the outcome of another 603.
609. Outer seen middle 26, 604 paired 604, extra 604, which makes the outcome of another 604.
610. Outer seen middle 27, 605 paired 605, extra 605, which makes the outcome of another 605.
611. Outer seen middle 28, 606 paired 606, extra 606, which makes the outcome of another 606.
612. Outer seen middle 29, 607 paired 607, extra 607, which makes the outcome of another 607.
613. Outer seen middle 30, 608 paired 608, extra 608, which makes the outcome of another 608.
614. Outer seen middle 31, 609 paired 609, extra 609, which makes the outcome of another 609.
615. Outer seen middle 32, 610 paired 610, extra 610, which makes the outcome of another 610.
616. Outer seen middle 33, 611 paired 611, extra 611, which makes the outcome of another 611.
617. Outer seen middle 34, 612 paired 612, extra 612, which makes the outcome of another 612.
618. Outer seen middle 35, 613 paired 613, extra 613, which makes the outcome of another 613.
619. Outer seen middle 36, 614 paired 614, extra 614, which makes the outcome of another 614.
620. Outer seen outer 1, 615 paired 615, extra 615, which makes the outcome of another 615.
621. Outer seen outer 2, 616 paired 616, extra 616, which makes the outcome of another 616.
622. Outer seen outer 3, 617 paired 617, extra 617, which makes the outcome of another 617.
623. Outer seen outer 4, 618 paired 618, extra 618, which makes the outcome of another 618.
624. Outer seen outer 5, 619 paired 619, extra 619, which makes the outcome of another 619.

625. Outer seen outer 6, 620 paired 620, extra 620, which makes the outcome of another 620.
626. Outer seen outer 7, 621 paired 621, extra 621, which makes the outcome of another 621.
627. Outer seen outer 8, 622 paired 622, extra 622, which makes the outcome of another 622.
628. Outer seen outer 9, 623 paired 623, extra 623, which makes the outcome of another 623.
629. Outer seen outer 10, 624 paired 624, extra 624, which makes the outcome of another 624.
630. Outer seen outer 11, 625 paired 625, extra 625, which makes the outcome of another 625.
631. Outer seen outer 12, 626 paired 626, extra 626, which makes the outcome of another 626.
632. Outer seen outer 13, 627 paired 627, extra 627, which makes the outcome of another 627.
633. Outer seen outer 14, 628 paired 628, extra 628, which makes the outcome of another 628.
634. Outer seen outer 15, 629 paired 629, extra 629, which makes the outcome of another 629.
635. Outer seen outer 16, 630 paired 630, extra 630, which makes the outcome of another 630.
636. Outer seen outer 17, 631 paired 631, extra 631, which makes the outcome of another 631.
637. Outer seen outer 18, 632 paired 632, extra 632, which makes the outcome of another 632.
638. Outer seen outer 19, 633 paired 633, extra 633, which makes the outcome of another 633.
639. Outer seen outer 20, 634 paired 634, extra 634, which makes the outcome of another 634.
640. Outer seen outer 21, 635 paired 635, extra 635, which makes the outcome of another 635.
641. Outer seen outer 22, 636 paired 636, extra 636, which makes the outcome of another 636.
642. Outer seen outer 23, 637 paired 637, extra 637, which makes the outcome of another 637.
643. Outer seen outer 24, 638 paired 638, extra 638, which makes the outcome of another 638.
644. Outer seen outer 25, 639 paired 639, extra 639, which makes the outcome of another 639.

- 645. Outer seen outer 26, 640 paired 640, extra 640, which makes the outcome of another 640.
- 646. Outer seen outer 27, 641 paired 641, extra 641, which makes the outcome of another 641.
- 647. Outer seen outer 28, 642 paired 642, extra 642, which makes the outcome of another 642.
- 648. Outer seen outer 29, 643 paired 643, extra 643, which makes the outcome of another 643.
- 649. Outer seen outer 30, 644 paired 644, extra 644, which makes the outcome of another 644.
- 650. Outer seen outer 31, 645 paired 645, extra 645, which makes the outcome of another 645.
- 651. Outer seen outer 32, 646 paired 646, extra 646, which makes the outcome of another 646.
- 652. Outer seen outer 33, 647 paired 647, extra 647, which makes the outcome of another 647.
- 653. Outer seen outer 34, 648 paired 648, extra 648, which makes the outcome of another 648.
- 654. Outer seen outer 35, 649 paired 649, extra 649, which makes the outcome of another 649.
- 655. Outer seen outer 36, 650 paired 650, extra 650, which makes the outcome of another 650.
- 656. Last final hidden, last paired last, extra last, which makes the outcome of another last.
- 657. Seeing something seen winner, paired 0, extra 0, which makes the outcome of another 0.
- 658. Seeing nothing hidden winner, the perpetually hidden 0.
- 659. Finally seeing nothing hidden winner, the finally hidden 0.

The list shown above is how the complete major set and complete minor sets of the verse are put together. Within the verse set, there are layers to it. To the major set of the verse, there contains individual pieces to that particular set place, such as the 1st seen winner models, where at first, which is absolute shown above in that list, there are the date mirror models. For each date mirror model stems into 4 year space models. For a year space model, it stems into 4 month timespace models. And for a month timespace model, it stems into 4 day time models. For each individual model of the major set of the verse, stems into a minor set with the associated date mirror models that stem into year space models of that particular minor set, and where those year space models stem into month timespace models of that particular minor set, and where those month timespace models stem into day time models of that particular minor set. There are

also associated twin paradoxes with the models of the verse, where the twin paradox explained goes as followed:

- If the paired models, then the extra model, however, if the extra model, then the outcome model, however, if the outcome model, then the paired models.

There is 4 pieces to a twin paradox, where each part of the major set and minor sets of the verse is grouped into 4 pieces, the paired models, the extra model, and the outcome model, where once the 4 pieces of the twin paradox are put together, that twin paradox is then named. For day time models of a particular level of the major set or minor sets, there exists an inner twin paradox, a middle twin paradox, an outer twin paradox, and a last final hidden twin paradox, where 4 models make the inner twin paradox, where that inner twin paradox stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes, then that middle twin paradox stems into an outer twin paradox comprised of 3 other middle twin paradoxes, and then that outer twin paradox stems into a last final hidden twin paradox comprised of 3 other outer twin paradoxes. Then for month timespace, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 models, and where then that inner twin paradox stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes, and then that middle twin paradox stems into an outer twin paradox comprised of 3 other middle twin paradoxes. Then for year space, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 models, and then from that stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes. Then for date mirror, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 mirror models. Then the last final hidden day time twin paradox, the outer month timespace twin paradox, the middle year space twin paradox, and the inner date mirror twin paradox are put together, and goes as followed:

- If paired inner date mirror twin paradox with middle year space twin paradox, then outer month timespace twin paradox, however, if outer month timespace twin paradox, then last final hidden day time twin paradox, however, if last final hidden day time twin paradox, then paired inner date mirror twin paradox with middle year space twin paradox.

In the paradox explained and shown above, the inner date mirror twin paradox is paired with the middle year space twin paradox, the extra is the outer month timespace twin paradox, and the outcome is the last final hidden day time twin paradox, where the name of this twin paradox is the century twin paradox.

With the major set and minor sets of the verse, there is an absolute paradox between the finally nothing seen winner 0, and the finally nothing hidden winner 0, where it goes as followed:

- If it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, it is therefore the finally nothing hidden winner 0, however if it is the finally nothing hidden winner 0, therefore it is the finally nothing seen winner 0. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the

finally nothing hidden winner 0. However if it is the finally nothing hidden winner 0, therefore it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, however if it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, it is therefore the finally nothing hidden winner 0. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the finally nothing seen winner 0. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the finally nothing seen winner 0 or the finally nothing hidden winner 0.

The outcome of the absolute paradox shown above produces another layer to the major set of the verse and is where the minor sets of the verse start from, that are connected to individual models of the major set, where the result of that absolute paradox is that it creates the nothing winner absolutely finally perpetually 0.

For a single date mirror model, there is 4 year space models that stem from that date mirror model, there is 16 month timespace models that stem from that date mirror model, and there is 64 day time models that stem from that date mirror model.

All people have a brain that is individual to them, and an individuals brain has macro properties, micro properties, nano properties, and quantum properties. The brain is mental, and is macro, and there is the macro verse that is a set of all possible macro things that exist within an individuals brain and also exist in the many worlds of the galaxy and cosmos. There is a mirror panel in the middle of an individuals brain. Brain models are made by mental matter, and on the left side of an individuals brain, is a standard clock in motion made out of mental matter that is neurons, and on the right side of an individuals brain is also another standard clock in motion made out of mental matter that is neurons. The property of neurons is that they have control. A macro model is applied on to the standard clock depending on what that individual will do, is doing, and has done. Then, there is the micro verse that is the set of all possible micro things that exist within the micro of a persons brain and also the micro of the many worlds of the galaxy and cosmos. And within a persons brain and specifically within the standard macro clock there is 4 standard micro clocks in motion made of genes, nuclei, cells, and membranes. A micro model is applied on to the micro standard clocks depending on what that individual will do, is doing, and has done. Then, there is the nano verse that is the set of all possible nano things that exist within the nano of a persons brain and also the nano of the many worlds of the galaxy and cosmos. And within a persons brain and specifically within the standard micro clock there is 16 standard nano clocks in motion made of squiggles, swirls, spirals, fractals, elements, molecules, compounds, and chemicals sewn together with needles, thread, and stitches. A nano model is applied on to the nano standard clocks depending on what that individual will do, is doing, and has done. Then, there is the quantum verse that is the set of all possible quantum things that exist within the quantum of a persons brain and also the quantum of the many worlds of the galaxy and cosmos. And within a persons brain and specifically within the standard quantum clock there is 64 standard

quantum clocks in motion made of essence, soul orbs, soul strings, soul waves, and soul fields. A quantum model is applied on to the quantum standard clocks depending on what that individual will do, is doing, and has done. Then, there is also 1 standard outside clock that is made of material existence that a person has outside of the brain and that encases that individual and that that individual sees outside of that standard clock to the world and things around them. The standard outside clock, the standard macro clocks, the standard micro clocks, the standard nano clocks, and the standard quantum clocks are all linked with each other and are synced with each other.

This set is timed at 18:19, and is dated as the 8th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.